

Process Conditions-based Tuneable Selective Catalysis of Hydroxymethylfurfural (HMF) Hydrogenation Reactions to Aromatic, Saturated Cyclic and Linear Poly-functional Alcohols over Ni–Ce/Al₂O₃

Received 00th January 20xx,
Accepted 00th January 20xx

DOI: 10.1039/x0xx00000x

Brett Pomeroy^a, M. Grilc^a, B.Likozar^{a*}

The related immense versatility of a ceria-promoted transition metal catalyst, utilized for the hydrogenation of 5-hydroxymethylfurfural (HMF), is demonstrated in this research study. We reveal a capability to achieve a selective considerable yield of three important high-valued HMF-derived compounds by simply modifying analysed reaction conditions or/and water-containing process medium.

Due to the rising concerns of climate change and pollution instigated from fossil fuel usage, lignocellulosic biomass as a renewable feedstock has been recognized as a sustainable replacement due to its availability and relatively low cost. Cellulose, the major component comprising approximately half of all lignocellulosic biomass, offers incredible potential as a source for chemicals and biofuels. Particularly, 5-hydroxymethylfurfural (HMF) has received immense attention for bio-based chemical production with enormous potential, even being described as a “sleeping giant”.¹ Obtained from the dehydration of glucose, HMF is a highly versatile intermediate which allows it to be converted into an assortment of value-added compounds. Notably, the diols 2,5-bis(hydroxymethyl)furan (BHMF) and 2,5-bis(hydroxymethyl)tetrahydrofuran (BHMTFH) have been considered extensively in the manufacturing of polyesters and heat insulating polymers which are presently made solely from fossil fuels.^{2,3} 1,2,6-hexanetriol (1,2,6-HT) can also be attained from HMF, a chemical that has tremendous value either directly as a moisturizing agent, solvent, and polymer cross-linker in certain resins and synthetic rubbers, or as an intermediate for the production of 1,6-hexandiol which is applied in the adhesive, coatings, and paint industry. 1,6-hexanediol has an approximate global market value of \$600 million USD, though currently is produced with relatively low yields from adipic acid originating from non-renewable sources.⁴ Hydrogenation has been widely established as an efficient method to convert HMF to these aforementioned value-added chemicals. Typically, it entails moderate temperatures up to 300 °C, high hydrogen pressures (up to 20 MPa), while in the presence of a heterogeneous catalyst.⁵ In terms of catalyst selection that is active for hydrogenation reactions, transition metals such as nickel are more desirable due to their low costs and availability despite their general inferior catalytic activity compared to noble metals such as Pt and Pd. Promoters in the form of a second metal (bimetallic) are necessary to improve catalyst

performance and tune selectivity towards more favourable products. While a diverse collection of high-valued chemicals can be obtained from HMF, most studies almost exclusively rely on a single catalyst to produce a single product, greatly limiting economic feasibility and industrial utility. As apparent in Table 1, several have independently achieved exceptional yields of BHMF, BHMTFH, or 1,2,6-HT, though generally require the presence of noble metals, extremely high loadings in the case of using Ni, utilize toxic solvents like 1,4-dioxane, implement miniscule initial amounts of HMF, and/or require exceptionally long reaction times of 12+ hours.

We demonstrate for the first time the remarkable flexibility of a single, transition metal catalyst with relatively low metal loadings, to form three major, bio-based compounds from HMF in significantly high yields by only adjusting the reaction conditions and/or medium. Ceria as a catalyst dedicated for hydrogenation purposes is rather uncommon in the literature as it is typically applied for oxidation reactions due to its high redox properties and oxygen storage capacity.^{6,7} Although, more unfamiliar is its capability to illicit both acidic-basic functionalities (amphoteric) depending on catalyst preparation and reaction conditions.^{8,9} Additionally, its water tolerance, suppression of coke formation, and prevention of active metal sintering makes ceria a favourable promoter.^{10,11,12} Based on the hypothesis of Dumesic et al. that metal oxides with high isoelectric points (IEP) were responsible for improved yields of ring saturated products by restricting acid-catalyzed degradation reactions, alumina was chosen as support material due to its relatively high IEP/point zero charge (PZC), along with its high surface area and low cost.¹³ We acknowledge that there can be a discrepancy between IEP and PZC values, where the former is determined by electrophoresis and the latter is determined by potentiometric titration¹⁴, but for simplicity purposes we report only PZC in this study as values were more frequently described in the literature. Two different alumina were investigated to validate this hypothesis; a pure γ -alumina with a reported PZC of 8.5, and another alumina with a lower PZC due to the presence of both α and γ phases.^{15,16} Furthermore, we have demonstrated the reaction to be effective in both monophasic water-THF and biphasic water-1-BuOH solvent systems, which together have been identified as solvent mixtures selective for HMF production from C₆ sugars.^{17,18} Though presently THF is not classified as a green solvent such as 1-BuOH, several studies have demonstrated the likely prospect of producing it from biomass-derived feedstocks such as maleic anhydride and furfural.^{19,18,20} Water as a co-solvent is obviously desired as a cheap and green solvent, while its presence also was identified to limit dehydration reactions and increase product selectivity towards desired products.

^a Department of Catalysis and Chemical Reaction Engineering, National Institute of Chemistry, Hajdrihova 19, 1000 Ljubljana, Slovenia

Electronic Supplementary Information (ESI) available: [details of any supplementary information available should be included here]. See DOI: 10.1039/x0xx00000x

Table 1. Comparative hydrogenation of 5-hydroxymethylfurfural over related catalysts.

Catalyst	Cat. amount	HMF	Solvent	Temp. (°C)	Pres. (MPa)	Time (h)	Conv. (%)	Selectivity (%) (BHMF, BHMTFH, 1,2,6-HT)			Ref.
20 mol% Cu ^a	0.016g	0.25 mmol	methanol	130	3	1	100	93	0	0	21
1wt.% Au ^a	0.01g	0.1M	water	60	6.5	2	100	96	0	0	22
1wt.% Ru ^b	0.2g	0.4g	1-BuOH/water	130	2.8	12	100	0	91	3	13
74wt.% Ni ^a	0.2g	1.5g	1,4-dioxane	60	6	6	100	4	96	0	23
Raney Ni (>93 wt.%) ^a	0.5g	1.5g	1,4-dioxane	100	1.5	30	100	0	96	0	24
1 wt.% Ru ^c	0.05g	0.4g	1-BuOH/water	130	2.8	1	100	0	53	13	13
5wt.%Pt+ 5wt.%Co ^b	0.01g	0.2 mmol	water	135	3	24	100	0	41	42	25
10wt.%Ni+ 15%wt.Ce ^a	0.1g	1g	THF/water	140	5	6	100	96	4	0	This work
			1-BuOH	190	5	3	100	0	88	9	This work
			THF/water	190	5	3	100	0	73	26	This work
			THF/water ^d	190	5	1	100	2	39	59	This work

^a supported on Al₂O₃ ^b supported on CeO₂ ^c supported on carbon ^d addition of CaO

The catalyst synthesis procedure, described in detail in ESI[†], is a rather simple, sequential incipient wetness impregnation of initially cerium, oven dried, calcined at 400 °C in air, then followed by nickel incorporation under the same conditions. SEM images with corresponding EDXS elemental mappings (Figure S.1) indicate that nickel and ceria are highly dispersed over the support, and the spent catalyst remains rather constant with no inclination of any major particle coarsening or sintering following reduction treatment or hydrogenation reaction. TEM images (Figure S.2) identified Ce clusters on the catalyst surface made up of individual ~9 nm Ce particles with a lattice fringe of 0.311 nm indicating CeO₂ (111) crystal plane. It was not possible to observe any distinct nickel particles in TEM. Diffraction lines corresponding with CeO₂ fluorite cubic cell (JCPDS# 00-004-0593) were clearly observed, although peaks were generally quite broad indicating poor crystallinity (Figure S.3). Ceria crystal size was estimated based on powder XRD spectra to be around 9nm which grew slightly to 11-12 nm in the spent catalysts (Table S.1). No nickel peaks matching to NiO or Ni-containing alloys were detected in XRD analysis of either Ni or NiCe catalysts, as well as in either of the spent catalysts (Figure S.4). This has been observed by others with similar Ni-Ce catalysts where Ni is proposed to be either in a highly dispersed amorphous state, or in <4 nm NiO crystallites which are below the detection limit.^{26,27} XRD analysis of the mixed Al₂O₃ support clearly indicates the presence of α -alumina phase and thus, contributed to a lower PZC relative to pure γ -alumina.¹⁶ Specific surface area (S_{BET}) and average pore volume (V_{p}) decreased marginally following Ni incorporation and for each sequential impregnation amongst the bimetallic NiCe catalyst (Table S.2). This designates that Ni and Ce particles blocked some porosity on the catalyst surface, yet the catalyst retained a reasonably high specific surface area even amongst the spent catalysts between 147-172 m² g⁻¹. XPS analysis of the

bimetallic NiCe catalyst exhibits the presence of both Ce³⁺ (v' and u') and Ce⁴⁺ (v, u, v'', and u'') oxidation states, although their precise quantification cannot be determined (Figure S.5). The Ni2p_{3/2} and Ni2p_{1/2} spectra indicate bands with binding energies at 855.6 eV and 873.5 eV, respectively, correlating well with Ni²⁺ from Ni(OH)₂.^{28,29} The Ce 3d spectra demonstrated a slight increase in peaks associated with Ce⁴⁺ and a decrease in peaks associated with Ce³⁺ after Ni was incorporated into the 15Ce catalyst. This would suggest that some of the ceria was oxidized from Ce³⁺ to Ce⁴⁺ in the presence of nickel species, possibly by weakening the interaction between Ce and the γ -Al₂O₃ support. TPR profiles for different supported and doped catalysts along with pure oxides were carried out for comparative purposes, and is shown in Figure S.6. Pure NiO demonstrated a distinct reduction peak between approximately 240 °C and 400 °C, accrediting to the reduction of NiO to Ni⁰. Thus, all catalysts were reduced prior to activity tests at 400 °C as it was expected to fully reduce all unalloyed Ni species. Pure CeO₂ resulted in moderate hydrogen consumption at elevated temperatures, although when impregnated onto the γ -Al₂O₃ support, reducibility was essentially eliminated. This advocates that Ce is interacting strongly with the alumina support, potentially forming a CeAlO₃ alloy.^{30,31} As a result of this, Ni-Ce bimetallic catalyst demonstrated superior reducibility compared to the Ni monometallic catalyst. The presence of CeAlO₃ has been reported to lessen the interaction between Ni and Al₂O₃, restricting NiO crystalline growth, improving dispersion, and enhancing reducibility.^{32,33} Reducibility of Ni supported on either alumina support proved to be practically equal below 400 °C. NH₃/CO₂/CO temperature-programmed desorption coupled to a mass spectrometer (TPD-MS) was performed to quantify acidic, basic, and metallic sites, respectively, and the calculated values are presented in Table S.3. The principal difference between Ni and NiCe catalysts were the number of acidic sites, where ceria incorporation cut acidity

almost in half compared to the monometallic Ni catalyst (289 vs. 502 $\mu\text{mol g}^{-1}$), yet acid strength remained consistent as shown in Figure S.7. The concentration of basic sites were identified to be identical between the Ni and NiCe catalysts with 70 $\mu\text{mol g}^{-1}$, and metallic sites provided from Ni were slightly higher with 71 $\mu\text{mol g}^{-1}$ compared to ceria-promotion with 61 $\mu\text{mol g}^{-1}$. Thus, the differences in the concentration of sites between the catalysts suggest that the ratio between acidic and basic sites could be an important aspect in the distinct formation of BHMTHF and 1,2,6-HT.

Scheme 1. Proposed reaction network of HMF hydrogenation.

Based on all detected intermediates and products during catalytic activity tests, a detailed reaction scheme is proposed in Scheme 1. The colours for each compound presented in the reaction network correspond with the colours displayed in all forthcoming figures depicting product selectivity and concentrations.

It was determined not possible under our reaction conditions to cleave the C-O bond amongst the saturated furan ring to convert BHMTHF directly to 1,2,6-HT, which has been reported to be possible by several other groups.^{4,34,35}

Figure 1a. Comparison of product selectivity between activity tests using different supports and dopants (Reaction conditions: 200 °C, 50 bar of H₂, 6 hours, THF as solvent). Figure 1b demonstrates the product selectivity as a function of time with 5Ni10Ce catalyst.

As shown in Figure 1a, the product selectivity between the different $\gamma\text{-Al}_2\text{O}_3$ supports and dopants varied significantly. In the absence of nickel, the monometallic Ce catalyst demonstrated negligible activity with only 2% conversion. When Ni was supported on the mixed γ and $\alpha\text{-Al}_2\text{O}_3$, complete conversion was achieved with an approximate product selectivity of 50% BHMTHF, 30% of BHMTHF, and 3% 1,2,6-HT, with the remaining products being mostly 2-HM-5-MF and THFA. When Ni was supported on pure γ -alumina, ring saturation reactions increased considerably yielding mostly BHMTHF along with moderate amounts of MTHFA. Ring opened products also emerged, though was namely 1,5-HD. As reducibility was almost identical, the presence of $\alpha\text{-Al}_2\text{O}_3$ in the support likely contributed to the substandard performance compared to the support which was determined to be exclusively $\gamma\text{-Al}_2\text{O}_3$, possibly as a result of the lower PZC. The incorporation of Ce prior to Ni resulted in dehydration reactions

being significantly impeded and in its place, BHMTHF production increased up to 70%. Ring opening reaction forming 1,2,6-HT also increased to 9%. Subsequently, an activity test was performed with lanthanum in place of ceria to validate the beneficial effect of ceria. When ceria was replaced with lanthanum, full conversion was still achieved but ring saturation and ring opening reactions were substantially hampered, constraining primarily to only BHMF. As observed in TPR, regardless of the substantial improvement in Ni reducibility with La impregnation instead of Ce, the NiLa catalyst demonstrated the lowest amount of BHMTHF and 1,2,6-HT (Fig. S.6). In conclusion, these results suggest that nickel reducibility was enhanced with the addition of ceria, although it does not appear to be the leading cause for the higher yields of BHMTHF and 1,2,6-HT. These results suggest that the higher PZC associated with the pure γ -alumina support in addition to the ceria promotion could play a crucial part in the optimal

formation of BHMTHF and 1,2,6-HT. Figure 1b presents the selectivity of detected intermediates and products as a function of time from the activity test performed with 5Ni10Ce catalyst. In the attempt to optimize BHMTHF and 1,2,6-HT yields as well as compressing reaction time, various Ni and Ce loadings were investigated with shorter activity tests of only 3 hours (Figure S.8). Results concluded that the catalyst composition containing 10 wt.% Ni and 15wt.% Ce performed the best with the highest selectivity of BHMTHF and 1,2,6-HT. Thus, this catalyst composition was subjected to further catalytic activity tests in the pursuit to optimize BHMTHF and 1,2,6-HT production.

Activity tests were carried out with reaction temperatures ranging from 140 – 200 °C to investigate the influence of temperature, as shown in Figure 2. When using only THF as solvent, temperatures below 170 °C were inadequate in converting past the initial reaction involving reduction of the aldehyde to produce BHMf. The highest BHMTHF selectivity of 85% was achieved at 170 °C. As reaction temperatures increased above 170 °C, successive dehydration reactions rose forming MTHFA and ring opened products increased including the occurrence of 1,5-HD and 1,5-PD. When water was incorporated into the reaction solvent system, dehydration reactions were virtually terminated causing BHMTHF and 1,2,6-HT to be practically the only final products. As reaction temperature increased from 170 °C to 200 °C in both THF and H₂O/THF solvent systems, the ratio between cis:trans isomers of BHMTHF decreased from 5.4/5.6 to around 4.7 (according to GC analysis and was verified by C¹³ NMR shown in Fig S.9 and Fig S.10). This is one of the highest trans BHMTHF isomer formations ever achieved from HMF as most literature exclusively report >95% cis isomer.^{36,37} This is likely a result of the lower Ni loadings and higher reaction temperatures

compared to most other studies, allowing the intermediate to more readily desorb following syn addition of the initial C=C, flip over, and reabsorb to subsequently hydrogenate the second C=C from the opposite side to produce the trans isomer. The highest 1,2,6-HT selectivity of 26% was achieved at 190 °C. The maximum BHMf selectivity of 96% in this study was also achieved at 140 °C when the reaction time was extended to 6 hours. Similar behaviour was observed when adding water to the reaction using 10Ni catalyst, yet 1,2,6-HT selectivity was substandard relative to 10Ni15Ce catalyst, reaching only 10% (Figure S.11a). An additional reaction was performed using 100mg each of 10Ni/Al₂O₃ and 15Ce/ Al₂O₃ which resulted in a minor increase of 1,2,6-HT selectivity to 15%, although still inferior to the bimetallic 10Ni15Ce catalyst (Fig. S.11b). This implies that the close proximity and/or interface between Ni and Ce particles are necessary for the enhanced ring opening yielding 1,2,6-HT.

As shown in Table 2, comparable results were also accomplished when applying monophasic 1-BuOH and biphasic water-1-BuOH solvent systems, even achieving the highest BHMTHF selectivity of 88% in this study. To supplement the assumption that point zero charge is a crucial aspect in the hydrogenation of HMF as previously cited, a selection of metal oxides with different point zero charges were added for activity tests utilizing water-THF as solvent. Each activity test included 0.1 g of 10Ni15Ce/ γ -Al₂O₃ catalyst alongside 0.5 g of metal oxide, and the results are presented in Table 2. Specifically, metal oxides were chosen considering their intrinsically high PZC (ZnO (~9), CaO (~11), and MgO (~12)) and are all relatively insoluble in water, permitting straightforward filtration prior to analysis of liquid samples.^{38,39,40}

Figure 2. Activity tests with reaction temperature from 140 – 200 °C with pure THF (a) and 5 vol.% H₂O in THF (b) as solvent. (Reaction conditions: 10Ni15Ce catalyst, 50 bar of H₂, reaction time of 3 hours.)

Interestingly, ZnO addition influenced product selectivity trivially compared to its absence. The incorporation of MgO did substantially increase ring opening formation yielding 1,2,6-HT up to 42%, though performed inferior to CaO despite its higher PZC. The addition of CaO drastically aided in the production of

1,2,6-HT, achieving a selectivity of 59% in just 1 hour after achieving the desired reaction temperature, the maximum accomplished in this study and also one of the highest reported in literature. These conclusions were contrary to the results achieved by Dumesic et al. previously stated above who

reported a distinct improvement in BHMTFH yields and decrease in ring opening reactions when similarly integrating MgO into the reaction system using 1 wt.% Ru catalyst supported on CeO₂.¹³ Results during recyclability tests also complement our hypothesis on the key role surface charge likely has in this reaction. As demonstrated in Figure S.12, the 10Ni15Ce catalyst maintained consistently high conversions above 90% for 5 continuous cycles of reactions in both THF and water:THF solvent systems. However, product selectivity changed significantly following the initial activity test where ring saturation and ring opening reactions were considerably impeded, leaving BHMF as the main product. NH₃/CO₂/CO-TPD analysis of the spent catalysts revealed considerable changes to the concentration of sites following reactions (Table S.3). Specifically, the concentration of basic sites were ~200% higher in the spent 10Ni15Ce catalysts compared to before the reaction, while metallic sites slightly increased. As this was independent to the inclusion of water, we believe this was a consequence of ceria which has been reported to permit extensive oxygen mobility from the bulk phase towards the catalyst surface via oxygen vacancies through (reverse) oxygen spillover effects.^{41,42} This increase in O²⁻ moieties (and decrease of acidic sites) on the surface of the catalyst is expected to lower its PZC relative to prior, similarly to what has been described elsewhere.^{43,44} These results suggest that the strong negative charge of the catalyst is possibly inducing a repulsive effect on the furan ring, preventing it from effectively adsorbing, although still allows adsorption via the carbonyl group. Overall, it would appear that the surface charge of the catalyst is undeniably an important factor on adsorption configurations during HMF hydrogenation, although additional aspects need to be carefully considered.

Table 2. Activity tests with varying solvents and metal oxides, 10Ni15Ce catalyst, 190 °C, 50 bar of H₂, 3 hours.

Solvent	Metal oxide	Conversion (%)	Product Selectivity (%)		
			BHMTFH	1,2,6-HT	Other
THF	-	100	76	12	12
Water-THF	-	100	72	26	2
1-BuOH	-	100	88	9	3
Water-1-BuOH		100	77	22	1
Water-THF	ZnO	100	77	23	1
	MgO	100	55	42	3
	CaO*	100	39	59	2

*1 hour reaction time

Conclusions

We conclude for the first time the capability of a single, alumina-supported, transition metal catalyst to generate high yields of three, industrially relevant, high-valued products from the hydrogenation of HMF by only changing the reaction conditions and/or medium. Furthermore, we demonstrate in this study the beneficial influence water has on limiting dehydration reactions and facilitating ring opening reactions in a biphasic solvent system in which one of the phases is water,

or monophasic systems containing water. The addition of solid metal oxides with high point zero charges further improved ring opening to form 1,2,6-HT, attaining one of the highest selectivities reported in the literature. Future work is underway to investigate the deciding factor(s) for regulating between furan ring hydrogenation and ring opening reactions.

Author Contributions

All authors had equal contributions.

Conflicts of interest

There are no conflicts to declare.

Acknowledgements

The authors would like to appreciatively acknowledge the financial support of by the EU Framework Program for Research and Innovation Horizon 2020 under Grant agreement no. 814416 (Reaxpro) and the ARRS (Program P2-0152 and postdoctoral research project Z2-9200).

References

- 1 K. I. Galkin and V. P. Ananikov, *ChemSusChem*, 2019, 1–8.
- 2 R. J. Van Putten, J. C. Van Der Waal, E. De Jong, C. B. Rasrendra, H. J. Heeres and J. G. De Vries, *Chem. Rev.*, 2013, **113**, 1499–1597.
- 3 C. Moreau, M. N. Belgacem and A. Gandini, *Top. Catal.*, 2004, **27**, 11–30.
- 4 J. He, S. P. Burt, M. Ball, D. Zhao, I. Hermans, J. A. Dumesic and G. W. Huber, *ACS Catal.*, 2018, **8**, 1427–1439.
- 5 A. V. Bridgwater, *Biomass and Bioenergy*, 2012, **38**, 68–94.
- 6 G. M. Mullen, E. J. Evans, B. C. Siegert, N. R. Miller, B. K. Rosselet, I. Sabzevari, A. Brush, Z. Duan and C. Buddie Mullins, *React. Chem. Eng.*, 2018, **3**, 75–85.
- 7 C. Papadopoulos, K. Kappis, J. Papavasiliou, J. Vakros, M. Kuśmierz, W. Gac, Y. Georgiou, Y. Deligiannakis and G. Avgouropoulos, *Catal. Today*, 2019, **355**, 647–653.
- 8 Z. Wu, A. K. P. Mann, M. Li and S. H. Overbury, *J. Phys. Chem. C*, 2015, **119**, 7340–7350.
- 9 L. Vivier and D. Duprez, *ChemSusChem*, 2010, **3**, 654–678.
- 10 Z. Zhang, Y. Wang, J. Lu, M. Wang, J. Zhang, X. Liu and F. Wang, *Inorganics*, 2017, **5**, 1–11.
- 11 N. Miletić, U. Izquierdo, I. Obregón, K. Bizkarra, I. Agirrezabal-Telleria, L. V. Barrio and P. L. Arias, *Catal. Sci. Technol.*, 2015, **5**, 1704–1715.
- 12 L. Yang, L. Pastor-Pérez, S. Gu, A. Sepúlveda-Escribano and T. R. Reina, *Appl. Catal. B Environ.*, 2018, **232**, 464–471.
- 13 R. Alamillo, M. Tucker, M. Chia, Y. Pagán-Torres and J. Dumesic, *Green Chem.*, 2012, **14**, 1413–1419.
- 14 M. Kosmulski, *Adv. Colloid Interface Sci.*, 2016, **238**, 1–61.
- 15 A. Pintar, J. Batista and I. Muševič, *Appl. Catal. B Environ.*, 2004, **52**, 49–60.

- 16 J. Sung, L. Zhang, C. Tian, Y. R. Shen and G. A. Waychunas, *J. Phys. Chem. C*, 2011, **115**, 13887–13893.
- 17 M. Sayed, N. Warlin, C. Hultberg, I. Munslow, S. Lundmark, O. Pajalic, P. Tunå, B. Zhang, S. H. Pyo and R. Hatti-Kaul, *Green Chem.*, 2020, **22**, 5402–5413.
- 18 J. Li, W. Zhang, S. Xu and C. Hu, *Front. Chem.*, , DOI:10.3389/fchem.2020.00070.
- 19 J. P. Lange and S. H. Wadman, *ChemSusChem*, 2020, **13**, 5329–5337.
- 20 KANETAKA J, ASANO T and MASAMUNE S, *Ind Eng Chem*, 1970, **62**, 24–32.
- 21 K. T. V. Rao, Y. Hu, Z. Yuan, Y. Zhang and C. C. Xu, *Appl. Catal. A Gen.*, , DOI:10.1016/j.apcata.2020.117892.
- 22 J. Ohyama, A. Esaki, Y. Yamamoto, S. Arai and A. Satsuma, *RSC Adv.*, 2013, **3**, 1033–1036.
- 23 X. Kong, R. Zheng, Y. Zhu, G. Ding, Y. Zhu and Y. W. Li, *Green Chem.*, 2015, **17**, 2504–2514.
- 24 X. Kong, Y. Zhu, H. Zheng, F. Dong, Y. Zhu and Y. W. Li, *RSC Adv.*, 2014, **4**, 60467–60472.
- 25 H. Kataoka, D. Kosuge, K. Ogura, J. Ohyama and A. Satsuma, *Catal. Today*, 2020, **352**, 60–65.
- 26 P. V. R. Rao, V. P. Kumar, G. S. Rao and K. V. R. Chary, *Catal. Sci. Technol.*, 2012, **2**, 1665–1673.
- 27 R. tang Guo, Y. Zhou, W. guo Pan, J. nan Hong, W. long Zhen, Q. Jin, C. gang Ding and S. yi Guo, *J. Ind. Eng. Chem.*, 2013, **19**, 2022–2025.
- 28 K. Han, T. Kreuger, B. Mei and G. Mul, *ACS Catal.*, 2017, **7**, 1610–1614.
- 29 X. H. Liu, W. Liu, X. K. Lv, F. Yang, X. Wei, Z. D. Zhang and D. J. Sellmyer, *J. Appl. Phys.*, , DOI:10.1063/1.3374468.
- 30 S. Damyanova, C. A. Perez, M. Schmal and J. M. C. Bueno, *Appl. Catal. A Gen.*, 2002, **234**, 271–282.
- 31 A. Iriondo, V. L. Barrio, J. F. Cambra, P. L. Arias, M. B. Guemez, M. C. Sanchez-Sanchez, R. M. Navarro and J. L. G. Fierro, *Int. J. Hydrogen Energy*, 2010, **35**, 11622–11633.
- 32 K. Kamonsuangkasem, S. Therdthianwong, A. Therdthianwong and N. Thammajak, *Appl. Catal. B Environ.*, 2017, **218**, 650–663.
- 33 X. Yang, J. Da, H. Yu and H. Wang, *Fuel*, 2016, **179**, 353–361.
- 34 J. He, S. P. Burt, M. R. Ball, I. Hermans, J. A. Dumesic and G. W. Huber, *Appl. Catal. B Environ.*, 2019, **258**, 117945.
- 35 T. Buntara, S. Noel, P. H. Phua, I. Melián-Cabrera, J. G. De Vries and H. J. Heeres, *Angew. Chemie - Int. Ed.*, 2011, **50**, 7083–7087.
- 36 X. Hu, R. J. M. Westerhof, L. Wu, D. Dong and C. Z. Li, *Green Chem.*, 2015, **17**, 219–224.
- 37 S. H. Krishna, D. J. McClelland, Q. A. Rashke, J. A. Dumesic and G. W. Huber, *Green Chem.*, 2017, **19**, 1278–1285.
- 38 P. Tengvall, *Protein interactions with biomaterials*, Elsevier Ltd., 2011, vol. 4.
- 39 N. A. Oladoja, I. A. Ololade, V. O. Olatujoye and T. A. Akinnifesi, *Water. Air. Soil Pollut.*, 2012, **223**, 1861–1876.
- 40 M. Farooq and A. Ramli, *2011 Natl. Postgrad. Conf. - Energy Sustain. Explor. Innov. Minds, NPC 2011*, 2011, 0–4.
- 41 A. Parastaev, V. Muravev, E. Huertas Osta, A. J. F. van Hoof, T. F. Kimpel, N. Kosinov and E. J. M. Hensen, *Nat. Catal.*, 2020, **3**, 526–533.
- 42 G. Balducci, M. S. Islam, J. Kaspar, P. Fornasiero and M. Graziani, *Chem. Mater.*, 2000, **12**, 677–681.
- 43 X. Hao, L. Quach, J. Korah, W. A. Spieker and J. R. Regalbuto, *J. Mol. Catal. A Chem.*, 2004, **219**, 97–107.
- 44 M. H. Derkani, A. J. Fletcher, M. Fedorov, W. Abdallah, B. Sauerer, J. Anderson and Z. J. Zhang, *Colloids and Interfaces*, , DOI:10.3390/colloids3040062.